

Opinion

*Ko Waikato te awa, Ko Ngāti Tahu Ngāti Whāoa te iwi.
Photo by Lara Taylor (a mokopuna of the Waikato).*

Learning How to Operate in Aroha

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In the last edition of SIL (January 2022), Dr Anne Poelina shared her Opinion on Indigenous water rights as the Chair of the Martuwarra Fitzroy River Council, and a Nyikina Warrwa Traditional Owner. Across the ditch from Te Whenua Moemoeā (the land of the dreamtime also known as Australia), in Aotearoa New Zealand, I think it is safe to say that tangata whenua (people of the land) stand with the Martuwarra Fitzroy River in the fight for Indigenous water rights. Here I contribute my Opinion as a Māori-Pākehā-Dutch woman, passionate about Indigenous and environmental justice and well-being. In 2012, an urgent inquiry began into Māori proprietary rights

in freshwater bodies and geothermal resources. It just so happens that my tūrangawaewae (place of standing) is adjacent to the Waikato River, and on top of geothermal resource. The application granted by the Waitangi Tribunal¹, was in response to Māori opposition to the Crown’s proposed sale of shares in state-owned power companies (including on the Waikato River). Thus began a national investigation into significant legal and political issues, including how Māori water rights and interests could be resolved and enabled alongside those of other users. The Crown has since acknowledged its obligation and ability to deliver ‘use and control’ to Māori through more appropriate decision-making roles and economic benefits (Waitangi Tribunal 2019:532). Regulation of water use that upheld Māori rights would also require a specific allocation for the exclusive use by iwi (tribes) and hapū (sub-tribes, family groups). The Tribunal contends that ‘this allocation would be inalienable other than by lease, and it should be perpetually renewable (as all consents are in theory, provided there is still allocable water available)’. However, despite the Tribunal’s confirmation of Māori proprietary rights in water, the Crown’s position with regard to redress remains opposed to any national settlement or generic share for Māori (Waitangi Tribunal 2019:521). All ethical breaches aside though, Māori could still achieve proprietary through resource management reforms and the current allocation system instead.

Rather than address the complexities of Māori water rights and allocations, the Crown has concentrated on constructing legislation and policy that only recognises and empowers the rights and mana (prestige and authority) of water itself rather than that of tangata whenua. As with elsewhere in the world, one of the rivers in Aotearoa, the Whanganui River, has been awarded legal personhood. This Treaty settlement outcome for the Whanganui River iwi recognised their genealogical connection to the river which is their ancestor, with its rights provided for by the resultant legislation [the Whanganui River Act] Te Awa Tupua (Whanganui River Claims Settlement) Act 2017. Alongside an isolated application of legal personhood to one particular water body, aspects of Te Ao Māori (the Māori worldview) are also being progressed at the national scale through policy and planning. The National Policy Statement for Freshwater Management (NPSFM) now includes an overarching principle, Te Mana o te Wai. A policy that recognises and empowers the mana of wai (water) itself. This principle is set to be embedded across wider policies and plans throughout Aotearoa, for implementation by regional and local authorities in collaboration with iwi and hapū and communities. This policy work has been carefully centred around water quality, whilst managing to avoid aspects of water quantity such as access, use and allocation rights. These philosophical shifts in policy and legislation accommodate aspects

aroaha ~ love, care, compassion • hapū ~ sub-tribes, family groups
iwi ~ tribes • koha ~ gift • mana ~ prestige and authority
mātauranga ~ knowledge • tāngata whenua ~ people of the land
taonga ~ treasures • Te Ao Māori ~ the Māori worldview
tikanga ~ a customary system of values and practices
tipuna ~ ancestors • wai ~ water
waimāori ~ freshwater • whakapapa ~ genealogy

¹The Waitangi Tribunal was established by the Treaty of Waitangi Act 1975. It is a permanent commission of inquiry that investigates and makes recommendations on claims made by Māori relating to Crown breaches of the Treaty of Waitangi (signed in 1840 by Māori chiefs and the British Crown).

of Te Ao Māori (the Māori worldview) through the recognition and empowerment of the mana of water itself. Arguably this leads water politics in Aotearoa in a better direction. However, these constructs that only recognise and provide for one or some Māori relational values (i.e. 'mana' or genealogical connections between a river and an iwi) also detract and distract us from explicitly recognising the mana of the people themselves who are indigenous to and interconnected with these lands and waters.

Perhaps it's coincidence, or just the best that the Crown can do. However, many of us – academics,

(freshwater) and the love and respect required for appropriate management of our ancestral waterways, taonga (treasures) passed down from Papatūānuku (our earth mother). This could, at a minimum, be created within the current policy settings, albeit with changes that elevate protection of and provision for cultural values alongside environmental values. More fundamentally, the proposition is that a reframing of environmental governance to one based on tikanga (a customary system of values and practices) and mātauranga-a-iwi/hapū (knowledge specific to iwi/hapū) will stimulate more caring attitudes to water across Aotearoa (refer Sec. 7)² – to enhance and

place) and papakāinga (communal Māori dwellings). Allocation Three, 'Ngā Koha Puna' (gifted waters), provides for commercial takes of water and includes Māori rights and interests related to the development and commercial enterprises (Fig. 2). The principles within the tikanga-based framework implement a true partnership approach to water governance and management (refer to Taylor *et al.* 2021 for further detail). This framework defines a stronger hierarchy of water values in which cultural values have an appropriate place, and explicitly provides for consideration of cultural flows and allocations in water allocation planning. It aligns with, and builds on, the most recent NPSFM which has adopted a hierarchy that values (in principle) the wellbeing of the water first. Unfortunately, the policy lacks an implementation framework or guidance to help realise this transition. The type of approach we advocate for – pragmatic, implementable and informed by inherited wisdom – would help re-conceptualise water governance and management for the twenty-first century, through much-needed change in our societal awareness, attitudes, and behaviours.

Three factors are critical to this allocation framework. One is that freshwater is appreciated as a taonga (treasure), and we argue that in order to achieve this outcome, the system also needs to be reformed for which we suggest an overarching bicultural policy Ngā Taonga Tuku Iho (treasures handed down from our ancestors) (Sec. 5). Two is Te Mana o te Wai, which is consistent with and supports the current overarching principle in the NPSFM. If the mana of the wai (which is our tīpuna and taonga) is truly upheld, then so is the mana of the people, the place, and the culture; emphasising the reciprocal nature of a tikanga-based management approach. Three, that Māori rights and interests are provided for, alongside others, in each of the categories. The allocation hierarchy in Fig. 2 means that the flow or volume of water in a waterbody that is left once the tīpuna are sustained can be shared among humans for our own use and well-being, including for commercial purposes if there is sufficient volume. This wai is a koha (gift) based on aroha (love, care, compassion) to be used respectfully, responsibly, and sustainably. The column on the left side of the framework (refer to Fig. 1) stresses the importance of equitable distribution across people, place, and time including generations. Decision-making for water allocation must be respectful and wise, ensuring sustainability of this taonga for future generations, a concept sometimes referred to by Māori as 'being a good tīpuna' for our future mokopuna. The column on the right side provides a set of guiding principles

Fig. 1. Ngā Puna Aroha – a tikanga-based water allocation framework.

activists, and everyday people – argue that these constructions are illustrative of the strategic and manipulation of a deeply ambivalent Crown. A fragile structure that is mindful of needing to show that it is 'doing the right thing' (demonstrated by the policy work around the mana and personification of water), but simultaneously refraining from going to the full extent to recognise and provide for the mana of the people themselves. That further step would require the Crown to share its assumed authority, and uphold the guarantee made by the Crown in the Treaty of Waitangi/Tiriti o Waitangi (1840) that Māori would be able to continue under the system or lore of tino rangatiratanga (sovereignty and self-determination) over their taonga katoa (all that they treasure). The relationship between the environment and our taonga (including but not limited to freshwater) is one of reciprocity, such that the mana and wellbeing of those taonga will require the equivocal mana and wellbeing of the respective iwi and hapū. Kaitiakitanga (the Māori ethic of care or guardianship which applies but is not limited to the environment) requires those communities to be able to exercise rangatiratanga; rangatiratanga, tikanga, and mātauranga-a-iwi/hapū. These are all Te Ao Māori concepts that are nested within a deep, holistic, values-based culture which cannot be disconnected and applied authentically if it is in bits and pieces (the way the Crown is currently trying to apply it, or more appropriately, trying to support application by Māori).

I want to share with you a framework that a few of us developed to assist the (seemingly perplexed) Crown to re-indigenise water allocation for Aotearoa. We called this framework Ngā Puna Aroha. This name reflects the springs or genesis of waimāori

protect the mauri (health and well-being) and mana (spiritual power, authority, prestige) of waimāori and, reciprocally, human communities.

The framework proposes a restructured system of water allocation, grounded in indigenous principles, which would provide the fundamental shift needed in our conception and use of freshwater. In Fig. 1, the first priority for allocation 'Ngā Tīpuna' (ancestors) ensures that the mauri (life force) and health of ngā tīpuna' must be provided for through an environmental baseflow and mauri allocation (and thus ecological well-being). Allocation Two, 'Ngā Mokopuna', (grandchildren) provides for 'priority' human and domestic consumptive purposes but includes water allocated for marae (tribal meeting

Fig. 2. Allocation hierarchy for Ngā Puna Aroha

² I will refer to "sections" throughout this article, by which I am referring to sections within the full article by Taylor *et al.* 2021.

to support such decision-making and implementation (refer to Box 2 Sec. 6).

If implemented, transitional limits would be required until values and allocations were established on a catchment basis through the NPSFM and Te Mana o te Wai. Catchments that are fully or over allocated would need proactive management with precautionary approaches informed by scientific knowledge as well as mātauranga, and by structured value assessments. While more clearly defined rights and interests would provide greater certainty and equity overall, a transitional phase would also be necessary to ensure existing users and consent holders are not unfairly prejudiced (MacPherson, 2017). With respect to a specific cultural allocation, in catchments where water has not been fully allocated, there is potential to put in place 'Mana Whenua Mana Wai' allocations (Fig. 2), the precedence for which has already been set by the reservations of water for Māori reserved lands undertaken by Tasman District Council (refer to Sec. 4 of Taylor *et al.*, 2021).

Fig. 3. Potential water-trading allocation framework based on the principles and proposed water allocation hierarchy of Ngā Puna Aroha

Water-trading markets may develop formally over time in Aotearoa (Fenemor, 2013), as has been the case in many other countries. Both Australia and Chile have included special provisions for their indigenous peoples (e.g. refer Jackson & Langton, 2011; Jackson & Barber, 2013; MacPherson, 2017). If markets are considered for Aotearoa, Ngā Puna Aroha could be used to assist with this consideration and potential market development. Fig. 3 is a simple illustration of where one might start, with the white area being unallocated water to be precautionary and to allow variability of residual flows.

If this approach were implemented then a water-trading allocation framework that was socio-culturally and ecologically just could potentially be considered in Aotearoa. While I don't necessarily advocate for water-trading, if Aotearoa shifted to a system that operates in aroha (Marsden, in Royal, 2003) it may offer efficient management that provides for the wellbeing of people, taonga, and place.

I have outlined Ngā Puna Aroha above to provide ideas for good practice for a regulatory system that reclaims and redefines the way that water is managed and protected (and potentially other taonga) for our shared future. Its legislative delivery could be achieved in multiple ways, which are considered in Taylor *et al.* (2021). The development of Ngā Taonga Tuku Iho would encompass all natural 'resource' management and provide a korowai (cloak) for the management of each particular 'resource' or taonga – and learning how to operate in aroha for our taonga that is freshwater, our lifeblood, is the best place to start.

Ko te wai te ora ng mea katoa

Water is the life giver of all things

In Aotearoa a whole-of-system transition to a Tiriti-based relational system, grounded in a new and formalised constitution is required (Taylor, 2022). Policies and legislation are important but must be supplemented with a commitment to a mutual learning process and re-institutionalisation by both Indigenous Māori and the Crown around genuine power-sharing and ways of operating ethically (Royal, 2000), ResponsAbility (Martin *et al.*, 2018) and in aroha (Marsden, in Royal, 2003) for our collective health and wellbeing. Further afield, I hope that this proposal to develop a dual water governance and management paradigm will inform and inspire freshwater and wider natural 'resource' management policymaking, regulatory frameworks, and implementation in other postcolonial nations. I welcome potential collaborators and thought-provokers to get in touch should this opinion-piece spark an interest.

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